

INTENSIVE METHODS OF TEACHING ENGLISH IN HIGHER GRADES

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Abstract: The article examines the technologies of intensive teaching of foreign languages in senior classes of secondary school. Intensive technologies contribute to the effective acquisition of the studied material in a short period of time.

Key words: intensive teaching, intensive teaching technologies, cooperative learning, language portfolio, English language.

In the methodology, intensive methods are considered as a specific system of training, which differs from the existing so-called traditional methods in a number of parameters. In terms of goals, intensive methods are aimed at achieving the maximum volume of assimilation of material in the shortest possible time. The content of training includes mastering a set of knowledge, skills and abilities sufficient to carry out activities in a certain area of communication [5]. The distinctive features of all intensive methods, which constitute their essence, are:

At present, sufficient experimental and practical material has been accumulated, testifying to the effectiveness of intensive methods. With their help, it is possible to form and activate the skills and abilities of practical language proficiency within a limited set of topics and situations that are of increased interest to students in a relatively short period of study time.

The conditions for teaching foreign languages using the intensive method in secondary school, first of all, writes Denisova L. G. [2], are connected with the need to take into account the social and age characteristics of schoolchildren. Experimental work has shown that the intensive method can be used when working with all age groups. The reasons for this are: the highest degree of personality development, an extensive information reserve, the desire to

understand the world through communication with other people, the presence of an initial language base. It is necessary to take into account age characteristics when selecting topics and communication situations, ensuring the substantive side of the educational process, and formulating communicative tasks.

In a secondary general education institution, English language classes in senior grades using the intensive method include:

During classes, students learn using intensive technology – learning in cooperation. The main idea of this technology is to create conditions for active joint learning activities of students in different learning situations. Students were united in small groups (3-4 people), they were given a common task, the role of each student in the group was discussed. Undoubtedly, the teacher plays a leading role at all stages of the learning process. In order to properly organize the learning activities of students, in order to subsequently achieve all the desired results, the teacher must properly organize the preparatory stage of work, educational material and teaching aids. The intensive course involves the introduction and consolidation of the studied material in one lesson. Students, having mastered the necessary lexical material, are ready to use it in practice. The activation of the studied lexical material takes place in 2 stages: communication training and communication practice.

According to Kitaygorodskaya G.A., classes at the communication training stage do not have a rigid structure, but are uniform in the sense that all course tasks are solved simultaneously in each lesson. This means that the lexical material received for the first time is worked out in all types of communication exercises [3]. After students have worked through the basic vocabulary on the topic being studied, it is necessary to consolidate the material studied. This stage involves a freer and more creative use of the educational material by students. The choice and use of language and speech tools are determined by the students themselves. To do this, the teacher only outlines the situation, without tying the student to a strict framework of tasks. Students work in collaboration. The teacher offers students specific situations on the topic being studied, distributes the necessary handouts, students compose dialogues or polylogues on the proposed plots independently in pairs or small groups, using new lexical units that will help them expand their vocabulary.

Another intensive technology was used in this course of study – a language portfolio. The main goal of a language portfolio is to adequately assess students' knowledge of the lexical material covered. Students assessed themselves independently, they do this not to get a grade, but to find out how far they have progressed in learning a foreign language. As was said above, the training was conducted using the following intensive technologies: collaborative learning technology and the use of a language portfolio as a learning technology.

The methodological approach of the intensive course excludes formal assignments, mechanical training of forms of linguistic phenomena and thus non-communicative use of language. It was necessary to create a natural speech environment for using the studied foreign language. To do this, the teacher needs to focus the students' attention on the semantic side of the statement. It is important to note that, first of all, it is necessary to interest the students. Intensive technology of teaching a foreign language can contribute to the effective assimilation of the material being studied in a short period of time, with the help of activating the material covered; students are able to overcome the language barrier and learn to communicate in a foreign language without any particular difficulties, since with the help of technology - learning in cooperation - the students did not have any problems, they solved all the issues that arose together.

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